

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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SBRT in liver metastases

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Stereotactic body radiotherapy (SBRT) is noninvasive treatment option for liver metastases in patients unsuitable for surgery.

Liver is a most common site of progression from gastrointestinal, lung and breast cancer. Surgical resection is treatment option with increased survival. Approximately 70-90% of liver metastases, however, are inoperable and an effective and safe alternative therapeutic option is necessary for these patients.

Stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT) in the treatment of patients with liver metastases has promising results, thanks to the ability of this procedure to deliver a conformal high dose of radiation to the target lesion in 1, 3 or 5 fractions and a minimal dose to surrounding critical healthy tissues.

SBRT provides good OS and LC for metastatic liver lesions. Higher SBRT doses ($BED_{10} \geq 100\text{Gy}$) and smaller tumor volumes ($< 40\text{ cm}^3$) are associated with improved LC and OS.

Key words: liver metastases, SBRT, dose

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